

Creating a national classification of the level of bus service provision: A case study of Wales

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Summary

There is a lack of research on public transport availability (PTA) at the national level. As the majority of work focuses on intra-regional and intra-city service provision, there is little understanding on how settlements are connected by PTA across large areas. K-means cluster analysis is used to classify the level of bus service provision for the 193 principal settlements in Wales. Bus service provision was modelled using OpenTripPlanner, Traveline National Dataset, and National Public Transport Access Nodes dataset. The 8 resulting clusters were analysed in relation to socio-economic and demographic characteristics and a classification of bus service provision is presented.

KEYWORDS: bus service provision, cluster analysis, accessibility, public transport availability, connectivity

1. Introduction

There has been a great deal of research in the UK and beyond on public transport accessibility (the ease at which people in an area can access key services or destinations using public transport) and far less research on public transport availability (PTA) – the level of public transport service provision in an area such as proximity to transport nodes, frequency of service, quality of service etc (Ryus et al, 2000; Sun & Thakuria, 2021). Research that has been undertaken tends to be focused on intra-city / intra-region service provision (eg Langford et al, 2012) with far less on larger city-regions, or wider regional, sub-national or national scales, and how settlements are connected more generally by PTA across wider geographical areas. Such research is fundamental for a deeper understanding of the geography of transport poverty (Sun & Thakuria, 2021) and the spatial inter-relationships of place dependency (Orford & Jones, 2021).

The aim of this research is to move towards addressing this gap by analysing the level of bus service provision for the whole of Wales. Bus service was chosen as buses are the dominant mode of public transport in Wales, accounting for nearly 7 in every 10 workers who usually commute by public transport in 2019 (Coombes & Rodrigues, 2023). The objective is to create a classification of the level of bus service provision to help researchers, practitioners and policymakers understand how different parts of Wales are connected by buses during different times of the day, different days of the week, including direct and transfer services. The classification will allow areas of Wales which have different levels of bus service provision to be mapped, compared and analysed in relation to socio-economic and demographic population characteristics, as well as employment, educational, and retail opportunities and local community services and assets. The research has emerged from a wider project on understanding public transport provision in Wales for people with disabilities and reduced mobilities and also the Understanding Welsh Places (UWP) project and uses data and methods developed as part of this work (<http://www.understandingwelshplaces.wales/en/>).

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2. Data and Methods

2.1 Data

This work uses the 193 principal Welsh settlements defined as Contiguous Built-up Areas (CBUAs) with a resident population of 2,000 people or over, a cut-off chosen to make robust statistical analysis possible. These places are also the origins and destinations of nearly all bus services in Wales. Bus service isochrones were generated using August 2021 data from Open Street Map (OSM) road network, bus timetables from Traveline National Dataset (TNDS), and bus stop locations from the National Public Transport Access Nodes dataset (NaPTAN). Additional explanatory variables include demographic and socio-economic data from the Census 2021, and an interdependence of place typology constructed during the UWP project (Orford & Jones, 2021).

2.2 Creating the bus service isochrones

OpenTripPlanner (OTP) was used to generate bus service isochrones for the 193 places. A python script queried all of the parameter combinations in Table 1, with journeys starting at 15-minute intervals within four time periods for weekdays, Saturdays and Sundays, including and excluding transfers.

Table 1: Parameters used to generate the bus service isochrones

Service parameters	Metrics
Transfer between service	No Transfers With Transfers
Day of the week	Weekday Saturday Sunday
Period of the day	Morning (7.00am-9.59am) Mid-day (4.00pm-6.59pm;) Evening (4.00pm-6.59pm) Night (7.00pm-6.59am)
Travel time (minutes)	10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90

The python script stored the GeoJSON response data in a PostgreSQL database resulting in approximately 27,800 isochrones. A maximum walking time of 1,600 metres to bus stops outside of urban areas was used to calculate isochrones. The *Count Overlapping Features* tool in the arcpy python library tallied the number of overlapping isochrones within each time period. Higher count areas experience more frequent service. Figure 1 shows the Pontypridd bus service for weekday mornings. Darker areas indicate more overlapping isochrones and a higher frequency of service.

Figure 1: Isochrone indicating Pontypridd’s bus service provision

2.3 Creating the classification of places by level of bus service provision

To compare the different levels of bus service provision, isochrones were classified using k-means clustering (Jones et al. 2021; Gale et al., 2016; Leventhal, 2016) on metrics including physical, demand, and supply characteristics. (Brochado, 2010). K-means was considered more appropriate than hierarchical or density-based clustering techniques because clusters are defined using the variance of the whole dataset, and each data point is assigned to a cluster group. Physical characteristics include geographic extent of service by both isochrone area and road network length, and bus stop density within an isochrone as a proxy for opportunities to catch a bus. A supply metric was applied by weighting these physical characteristics by the frequency of service. Given that our classification focuses on the level of bus service provision we excluded demand characteristics from the cluster analysis, opting instead to use demand metrics, such as demographic characteristics of the local population, as explanatory variables.

Based on collinearity diagnostics (Gale et al., 2016), isochrones based on transfers, weekday and Sunday, morning and night, and 20, 45 and 90 minute travel times, captured the majority of statistical variations in service coverage. Isochrone road network length was also selected over isochrone area as a measure of geographic service extent. Preliminary analysis indicated that the capital city of Cardiff substantially skewed the results and so was omitted from the cluster analysis, becoming its own group. Python’s *sklearn* package’s k-means clustering algorithm was run on metric z-scores, setting the initial centres using the *k-means++* parameter for 100 initializations and a maximum of 300 iterations. Nine solutions with generated for between 2 and 10 cluster groups and cluster diagnostic tests (Jones et al., 2021; Vickers et al., 2005; Gale et al., 2016; Leventhal, 2016) suggested that a 7 cluster solution provided the best discrimination, meaning a final classification of 8 groups including Cardiff.

3. Analysis and Findings

Figure 2 presents the cluster spatial distribution. Cluster characteristics are shown in figures 3 and 4.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of clusters of Wales' principal places by their bus service

Detailed pen portraits of the cluster groups are available on request. Key findings indicate bus services of places in Groups 0, 1 and 5, which tend to be smaller and more dependent, are characterised by high density of bus stops with relatively low road network coverage. This suggests that these places are more self-contained, with a well served core and limited connectivity further afield. Conversely, places in Groups 2, 4 and 6, which tend to be larger and more interdependent, have relatively high coverage of the road network, but with low bus stop density. This suggests that buses travel further afield, but there are relatively fewer opportunities to interact with the bus service across the isochrone area. Places in Group 3 tend to be small and independent and have the lowest bus service provision, suggesting that they are more self-contained, whereas Group 7 (Cardiff) is distinctly different to the other groups.

The metrics indicate that poor off-peak services in Group 1, which are often small dependent places on the urban outskirts may pose a problem for bus users who wish to access services in nearby places. Metrics for Groups 2 and 5 suggest these places retain good off-peak services, particularly on Sunday Night and there appears to be spatial clustering between Group 0 and Group 1 and Group 2 and Group 6. These findings warrant further investigation.

Figure 3: Radial plots show z-scores for bus service metrics by cluster group

Figure 4: Radial plots showing percentage of places by population size and interdependency by cluster group

4. Conclusions

The aim of this paper was to fill a gap in the literature by undertaking research into national PTA by analysing the level of bus service provision in Wales. We created a classification of Wales' 193 principal settlements by their level of bus service provision. Policymakers and professional practitioners may find this useful when trying to better understand how bus services within their place perform when compared to other places in Wales, particularly those places shown (by tools such as UWP's place classification) to have similar demographic and socio-economic characteristics to their own. Future work will look unpick these patterns further using the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of a place. For example, more work is needed to investigate why the bus service in some places outperforms that in others.

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7. Biographies

Scott Orford is a Professor in GIS and spatial analysis at Cardiff University School of Geography and Planning and WISERD. His research focusses on the spatial and statistical modelling of social and economic processes.

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